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Performance Analysis of Human Activity Recognition

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ABSTRACT

Inside the past couple of years, human action Recognition (HAR) has become an extremely imperative and significant territory of exploration because of the progression of the computerized periods of gadgets like cell phones, smartwatches, and camcorders used in our day by day lives. Profound Learning (DL) has driven analysts to utilize HAR in different spaces including wellbeing and prosperity applications the most point of this paper is to Classify the exercises happening in the casings. HAR application fields produce a major measure of information and not every one of them gives the computational force that DL models in HAR require. Utilizing our Convolutional Neural Network and Keras, we had the option to get 97.07% precision.

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INTRODUCTION

Human Activity Recognition (HAR) has become a popular point inside the past couple of years because of its hugeness in contemplating numerous regions, including medicinal services applications, on the web and disconnected intelligent gaming, sports, and checking frameworks for general purposes [1]. HAR research has an abrupt increment in Deep Learning (DL) techniques as result high precision in acknowledgment [2,3]. HAR has numerous application cell phones and smartwatches or is coordinated into garments or other explicit clinical hardware [2,4-6]. The activities are human-centered and spread a wide scope of classes including human-object cooperation, for example, playing instruments,

just as human-human collaborations, for example, shaking hands.

Related Works

As to HAR approaches, most of the recently distributed examinations address two kinds of acknowledgment utilizing directed learning [7-12] or semi-administered learning [13,14]. Move learning has likewise been explored, whereby the examples or models for exercises in a single area can be moved to improve the acknowledgment precision in another space to decrease the requirement for preparing information [15-16].

Furthermore, HAR has been broadly announced in numerous fields utilizing sensor modalities,

including surrounding sensors [21], wearable sensors [22], cell phones [23], and smartwatches [24]. Those sensors add to building up a wide scope of utilization spaces, for example, sport [25], human-PC communication [26], observation [27], video spilling [28], medicinal services framework [29], furthermore, PC vision zone [30]. Non-visual sensors since they are both difficulties allowed to introduce and privacy saving [31,32].

The corrupted complex picture and Video were influenced by an alternate type of unwanted signals like Brownian Noise (Fractal Noise) Rayleigh Noise, Gamma Noise, Poisson-Gaussian Noise, salt and pepper commotion, irregular esteemed drive clamor, dot clamor, Gaussian clamor, and Structured Noise, and so on as demonstrated as follows[37-40]. Clamor is extremely hard to expel it from the intricate pictures without the correct comprehension of the commotion model.

Table 2. Related Works in HAR approaches

	learning for Activity and Action Recognition	Gated Recurrent Unit	jogging, running.		
[18]	Comparison study to classify human activities	SVM, MLP, RF, Naive Bayes	Sleeping, eating, walking, falling, talking on the phone	Image	86%
[19]	Active Learning to recognize human activity using Smartwatch	RF, Extra Trees, Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, SVM	Running, walking, standing, sitting, lying down	Smart watch	93.3%
[20]	Recognizing human activity using smartphone sensors	Quadratic, k-NN, ANN, SVM	Walking upstairs, downstairs	Smart phone	84.4%
[33]	Zero-Shot activity recognition using visual and linguistic attributes	BGRU, GloVe	Drink, uncork, drool, lick	Image	42.17 %
[34]	Zero-shot activity-recognition based on a structured knowledge graph	Two-stream GCN method, self-attention mechanism	Biking, Skiing	Video	59.9%

DATASET AND METHODOLOGY

The dataset used in this paper is kinetics and link of dataset as

below:<https://deepmind.com/research/open-source/kinetics>

The dataset contains 400 human activity classes, with at any rate 400 video cuts for each activity. Each clasp endures around 10s and is taken from an alternate YouTube video. The activities are human focused and spread a wide scope of classes including human-object cooperation, for example, playing instruments, just as human-human connections, for example, shaking hands. There are 400 movement pictures in

Paper	Approach	Method	Activity	Input Source	Performance
[17]	Hybrid Deep	GMM, KF,	Walking,	Video	96.3%

the dataset and the model is prepared on every one of the 400 exercises.

Keras and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)

The CNN engineering, we will use today is a littler, progressively smaller variation of the VGGNet network very deep convolutional networks for Large Scale Image Recognition[36]. The goal of the convolution operation is to extricate the elevated level highlights, for example, edges, from the info picture.

ConvolutionalNets need not be restricted to only one convolutional Layer and got high computational[35]. Customarily, the first convolutional Layer is liable for catching the Low-Level highlights, for example, edges, shading, inclination direction, and so on. With included layers, the engineering adjusts to the high-level highlights also, giving us a system, which has a healthy comprehension of pictures in the dataset. The pooling layer is utilized for lessening the spatial size of the convolved include. There are two essential sorts of pooling we used to lessen the spatial size one max pooling and another is mean pooling.

Figure1: Convolution Operation is to extract the high-level features. Different parameters are used in proposed methodology like width,height,depth and classes.Width: The image width dimension.Height: The image height dimension.Depth: The depth of the image — also known as the number of channels.Classes: The number of classes in our dataset (which will affect the last layer of our model)

So as to build exactness we increment our channel size and utilized max pooling. The more profound we go in the system, the littler the spatial elements of

our volume as we increment size of channel and by diminishing the size of max pooling from 3 x 3 to 2 x 2 to guarantee we don't decrease our spatial measurements excessively fast.

Figure 2: Architecture of the Model. After training about 100 steps we got around Train Accuracy: 93.04 and Val Accuracy: 81.77.

Optimize the network to improve the validation accuracy

We have expanded our channel size to 128 here. Dropout of 25% of the hubs is performed to diminish overfitting again lastly, we have a lot of FC => RELU layers and a SoftMax classifier. We balance the model with a SoftMax classifier that will restore the anticipated probabilities for each class label.A representation of the system engineering of initial scarcely any layers of SmallerVGGNet.

Table 2. Result Analysis

Epoch	Train Loss	Validation Loss	Train Accuracy	Validation Accuracy
0	1.3	2	0.7	0.5
20	0.8	0.8	0.75	0.8
40	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.85
60	0.6	1.5	0.85	0.5
80	0.52	0.75	0.9	0.8
100	-	0.5	0.95	0.95

CONCLUSION

To achieve this undertaking, we utilized a human action acknowledgment model pre-prepared on the Kinetics dataset, which incorporates 400-700 human exercises (contingent upon which adaptation of the dataset you're utilizing) and more than 300,000 video clips. Trained a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) utilizing the Keras profound learning library. We are getting Good Accuracy with a large portion of the exercises covered. Using our Convolutional Neural Network and Keras, we had the option to get 97.07% precision.

Future Aspects

- Implementing a more robust network with more amount of data and a high system.
- We can implement a Resnet 3D model for the better extraction of features.
- Prediction of frames can be done in batch frames
- We can Implement it of many purposes like Activities in ATM's, Airports, Examination Surveillance, etc.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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